

Zakah, a function of Muslim authority and polity to effect streamlined collection and distribution

Mohamed Tariq Kahn

Allah says in the Quran al-Kareem:

[Surah Taubah, 60] " The Sadaqat (prescribed alms-Zakah) are only to be given to the poor, the needy, to those employed to collect them, to those whose hearts are to be won, in the cause of the slaves and those encumbered with debt, in the way of Allah and to a wayfarer. This is an obligation prescribed by Allah. Allah is All-Knowing, Wise."

Enjoining the good and forbidding the wrong is part of cleansing. It is an advice which we as Muslims must take on, and it is perfectly empowered in the principle of Zakah, a kind of charity, which linguistically means - to clean or purify, by giving as an obligation to those who deserve it.

The word Sadaqat, which means charity in general, is used sometimes interchangeably with the word Zakah, in the Quran. However it is important to differentiate between the two actions appropriately. Zakah requires a wealth limit and a waiting period of a year on that wealth, if it is monetary or in hand, in order to become liable to dispose of a specified amount, being 2.5%, for distribution to 8 categories of persons. Sadaqat in general is anything given, or even any goodwill or kindness at any specific time, to encourage a spirit of giving and sharing amongst people. There is yet another kind of Sadaqat, which is a poll tax (per head), applicable to the month of Ramadan only. This Sadaqat is to be given in staple food, the amount of one Sa' (about 2 litres by volume), of any non-perishable food or grain. Since its intent is to "cleanse" the fasting of Ramadan from any possible defects that might have occurred during its observation, it is also referred to Zakah-al-Fitr.

The Islamic economists vision of an effective economy is one that is expected to be based on the Qur'an and the Sunnah. Being Faith based makes this more ideal than the secular models of economy. This involves such norms where, as indicated by Mannan, of the International Center for Research in Islamic Economics, the action of payment skipping and avoidance (in paying taxes), which plagues all Western democratic systems, is not going to be as problematic when gain extends to the next world as well. (Kuran, 1986).

Establishing a modality of social justice, exemplified in the tenet of Zakah, can essentially **only be in the manner that Allah willed** when he sent His Messenger with the Deen over 1400 years ago. In this age, Zakah, the third pillar of Islam, is severely undermined and is not at all practised the way it ought to be. It has been turned into private charity, sadaqat, to a large degree. Enjoining the right in its application, and forbidding the wrong in what has happened to it in our time, is certainly a matter which deems attention. Surah Taubah is called to mind where Allah commands that Zakah be TAKEN, in order to cleanse.

"Take from their wealth the Zakah to cleans themselves therewith" [Quran 9:103]

Zakah is thus a public matter on which the Muslim ruler, or Amir (king, sultan, president), has a right in the Amwal Dhahirah (apparent wealth such as livestock, agricultural or minerals

etc.), as well as the Amwal Batinah(concealed wealth) such as gold and silver or merchandise, on behalf of the poor. One of the key features that make Zakah therefore different is the requirement for Muslim leader for every Muslim society, no matter where they find themselves, under whose auspices the Zakah is collected and distributed, and who pray for them. Ibn Qutayba and others understands on this verse that whenever Zakah/sadaqa was paid, the Prophet prayed for the cleansing/forgiveness of the donor's sins (Suliman Bashear, 1993). This is not the domain of a Zakah Fund (which in fact is registered as a charity!). Hundreds upon hundreds of registered charities exist today, each claiming to be authorised to collect Zakah. One does not have to be a rocket scientist to see the untenable situation of overlap, both in collection and distribution that creates many inefficiencies and problems in the proper discharge of this duty amongst Muslims.

During the Prophet's time, any person possessing 200 dirhams (600gr of Silver equivalent to US\$330.00) for a period of one year or having any other item of wealth to the extent of its Nisab limit was considered to have reached the *Zakatable* state of wealth (an excess wealth) and was, on that account, liable for Zakah, while a person possessing an amount below the Nisab limits, was a lawful beneficiary of Zakah. The highest priority receivers of the Zakah was the fuqara (poor) and masakin (needy). Human Development Report (2002), for instance, places 21 Muslim countries out of the 57 members in the Organisation of Islamic Conference, amongst the 36 least developed countries in the world, mainly in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia.

Muslim poverty levels were addressed by Muhammad Zubair Mughal, CEO of Al-Huda Centre of Islamic Banking and Economics spoke at the Islamic Microfinance Symposium in Tunis, March 2014. Here he highlighted that half of global poverty reside in the Muslim world while the Muslim population is 24% of the total global population. This is an alarming observation and indicates a serious disparity in terms of massive wealth agglomeration in a few Muslim states while the majority of the Muslim worlds are actually below the Nisab level by several degrees. (Muhammad Zubair Mughal, 2014)

Shaykh Yusuf al-Qardawy has divided those who deserve Zakah from al-fuqara and al-masakin into three categories: (Al-Tayib Zein Al-Abdin, 2003).

1. Those who have neither property nor a source of income.
2. Those who have some property or income but it is less than half of their basic needs.
3. Those who have some property or income, which covers half of his basic needs but does not meet all of them.

Lack of local community leadership means that the poor is dealt with on an ad-hoc and often disparate manner.

The Quranic categories, which is the basis for the jurists classification of those worthy to receive Zakah, is much higher than that specified by the international agencies. The Western or Non-Muslim Agencies speak only about food, medicine and clothing, being an extension of Maslow's hierarchy of needs. In contrast where Zakah laws in Muslim countries are employed by states, such as Sudan, the use of simple and flexible definitions of those who deserve Zakah are used. Thus al-fuqara is termed: "those who do not possess their food for one year...It includes the full-time student who cannot meet the expenses of his study". (Al-Tayib Zein Al-Abdin, 2003).

Conclusion:

Zakat collection and distribution have been based mostly regionally. This does not adequately address the disparities mentioned above. The Organization of Islamic Conference created a body called International Zakat Organization which eyed 2.5 Billion US\$ for collection in 2009 but has not since realised an effective model to collect and distribute Zakat internationally. A possible model for global Zakat by means of a new proposal for an International Zakat Agency Co-ordinating Council (IZACC) is indicated below:

In this way an international poverty alleviation programme to Muslim recipients in poverty stricken areas can be properly addressed as local community leaders and a proper record of the poor can be kept. The Fiqh rules applicable to Zakat in local regions can also be effectively adhered to, while at the same time surplus funds from the wealthy Muslim states can find their way to a more equitable distribution to actual poor and needy recipients by means of the IZACC. This method will also reduce risks associated with several independent organizations and international bodies collecting zakat on behalf of political and other causes, which have seen zakat funds being frozen under increasing international clampdowns on money laundering. Allahu alam.

References

Kuran T, 1986, The Economic System in Contemporary Islamic Thought: Interpretation and Assessment, International Journal of Middle East Studies, Vol. 18, No. 2 (May, 1986), pp. 135-164

Suliman Bashear, 1993, On the Origins and Development of the Meaning of Zakah in Early Islam, Arabica, T. 40, Fasc. 1 (Mar., 1993), pp. 84-113

Al-Tayib Zein Al-Abdin, 2003, The Disbursement of Zakah, Islamic Studies, Vol. 42, No. 1 (Spring 2003), pp. 127-136

Muhamad Subair Mughal, Online, March 2014, Islamic Microfinance Symposium, [<http://www.alhudacibe.com/imhd/news22.php>] accessed 25 June 2017

Al Quran Kareem, translation by Mufti Taqi Usmani, available at [<http://www.central-mosque.com/>]